

SYNTHESIS OF [TRIAQUA- μ_3 -OXIDO-HEXA(3-HYDROXYBENZOATO)TRIIRON(III)] CHLORIDE DIHYDRATE

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Hydroxybenzoic acids and their metal complexes have attracted growing interest because of their structural adaptability, biological activity, and coordination potential.

ABSTRACT

*A newly synthesized iron(III) coordination compound, $[Fe_3(O)(C_7H_5O_3)_6(H_2O)_3] \cdot Cl \cdot 2H_2O$ (Compound 1), was successfully prepared and structurally characterized. The complex was obtained by reacting $FeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ with *m*-hydroxybenzoic acid under mild hydrothermal conditions. X-ray diffraction analysis revealed that the compound crystallizes in a triclinic system featuring a trinuclear Fe^{3+} core bridged by a central μ_3 -oxo atom and surrounded by six *m*-hydroxybenzoate ligands. The molecular configuration, hydrogen-bonding interactions, and supramolecular framework were elucidated through single-crystal X-ray diffraction studies.*

A newly synthesized iron(III) coordination compound, $[Fe_3(O)(C_7H_5O_3)_6(H_2O)_3] \cdot Cl \cdot 2H_2O$ (Compound 1), was successfully prepared and structurally characterized. The complex was obtained by reacting $FeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ with *m*-hydroxybenzoic acid under mild hydrothermal conditions. X-ray diffraction analysis revealed that the compound crystallizes in a triclinic system featuring a trinuclear Fe^{3+} core bridged by a central μ_3 -oxo atom and surrounded by six *m*-hydroxybenzoate ligands. The molecular configuration, hydrogen-bonding interactions, and supramolecular framework were elucidated through single-crystal X-ray diffraction studies.

Hydroxybenzoic acids and their metal complexes have attracted growing interest because of their structural adaptability, biological activity, and coordination potential. Among these, 3-hydroxybenzoic acid (*m*-hydroxybenzoic acid) is a naturally occurring phenolic compound found in various plant sources such as grapefruit, olive oil, and medlar fruit. It is widely utilized in pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and food industries due to its antioxidant and antimicrobial effects [1]. The coexistence of carboxylic and phenolic functional groups enables this ligand to form thermodynamically stable complexes with transition metals, enhancing catalytic and biological properties [2]. Crystallographic and thermodynamic investigations have shown that 3-hydroxybenzoic acid exhibits polymorphism with diverse hydrogen-bonding arrangements, influencing its physicochemical characteristics and reactivity [3, 4]. Because of these structural features and its ability to coordinate through carboxylate oxygen atoms, it serves as an excellent model ligand for exploring structure–property relationships in

coordination chemistry. Moreover, hydroxybenzoic acids contribute significantly to biological systems as antioxidants and enzyme modulators, helping prevent cardiovascular and metabolic diseases [5].

Iron coordination complexes are of special significance due to their diverse structural architectures and potential applications in catalysis, magnetism, and bioinorganic chemistry. Carboxylate ligands, especially hydroxybenzoates, promote the formation of robust metal frameworks with versatile coordination geometries. We successfully synthesised and structural elucidation of a new trinuclear iron(III) complex, $[\text{Fe}_3(\text{O})(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_3)_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]\cdot\text{Cl}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (fig. 1), obtained from $\text{FeCl}_3\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and m-hydroxybenzoic acid under hydrothermal conditions.

Fig. 1. The crystal structure of the compound 1 (probability 25%)

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